

PREVENTION OF KIDNEY DISEASES IN ADOLESCENTS

Rasulova Nilufar

Associate professor of the Department of Public Health, Healthcare Management of the Tashkent
Pediatric medical institute

Aminova Asalya

4th year students of the Medical and Pedagogical faculty of the Tashkent Pediatric medical
institute

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Abstract. *Kidneys play an important role in maintaining the constancy of the "internal environment" of the body. In the fetus, they begin to function already for 3-4 weeks. Urination is observed in the fetus at week 9 of intrauterine development. Immediately after birth, the kidneys become the main organ of excretion of metabolic products and thereby maintain the constancy of the composition of its internal environment. Prevention of kidney diseases from an early age helps to avoid pathologies in the teenage period of life.*

Keywords: *neurological diseases, early diagnosis, medical examination, hemodialysis.*

ПРОФИЛАКТИКА ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ ПОЧЕК У ПОДРОСТКОВ

Аннотация. *Почки играют важную роль в поддержании постоянства «внутренней среды» организма. У плода они начинают функционировать уже на 3-4 неделе. Мочеиспускание наблюдается у плода на 9 неделе внутриутробного развития. Сразу после рождения почки становятся главным органом выделения продуктов обмена и тем самым поддерживают постоянство состава своей внутренней среды. Профилактика заболеваний почек с раннего возраста помогает избежать патологий в подростковом периоде жизни.*

Ключевые слова: *неврологические заболевания, ранняя диагностика, диспансеризация, гемодиализ.*

INTRODUCTION

The kidneys repeatedly pump our blood through themselves during the day and participate in the liberation of the body from the end products of metabolism, foreign and toxic substances, toxins, maintain water-salt and acid balance, blood pressure, immunological condition. All kidney diseases can be divided into 2 main groups: congenital or hereditary and acquired. Special attention should be paid to a woman's pregnancy from the very beginning of life, since the improper formation of the organs of the urinary system affects their function and leads to the emergence of pathological processes. Of great importance for the proper development of a child are the period of newborn, infancy, preschool age and early school age. Various viral diseases affect the development of kidney diseases. Vaccination, early detection and treatment of such diseases are necessary.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Recently, there are new kidney diseases associated with unfavorable environmental pollution of the environment with heavy metals, radionuclides, chemicals. Children living in regions with high levels of heavy metals are recommended to carry out preventive course activities, including an increased drinking regime, potato-cabbage diet, courses of taking antioxidants, vitamin therapy. The presence of atopic diathesis in a child requires allergological examination and treatment. In addition to skin and respiratory tract damage, the development of

atopic nephrotic syndrome is possible. The presence of reduced immunity and dysbiosis provide for the use of appropriate treatment, since these conditions can provoke the appearance of various diseases, including nephropathies of an exchange, immune or microbial-inflammatory nature.

RESULTS

There is an increasing number of cases of kidney disease in children born to parents who consume a lot of alcohol and use drugs. For the prevention and timely detection of kidney and urinary tract pathology, it is necessary:

- Early diagnosis of kidney condition.
- Timely treatment of foci of infection.
- Maximum restriction of contacts with patients suffering from viral diseases.
- Avoid hypothermia of the body
- Promptly inform the doctor about the existing hereditary diseases of parents, brothers, sisters. The presence of kidney diseases in the mother is a high risk factor for the development of kidney diseases in the child.
- Proper organization of the lifestyle and physical activity.
- Education of the child's food priorities (eating a small amount of salt, canned food, smoked and fried food).
- High and low blood pressure may indicate kidney disease.
- Undergo regular medical examination, including monitoring the state of kidney function.
- Correct solution of vaccine prevention issues.

For various diseases of the kidneys and urinary tract, the appropriate diet is prescribed by the doctor. But for any kidney diseases, fruits and vegetables are useful – cucumbers, pumpkin, cabbage, sweet peppers, watermelons, melons, apples, pears, dried apricots, prunes. Fresh herbs are useful – parsley, dill, celery, infusions of lingonberry leaves, strawberries, rosehip fruits, oat broth. Excessive protein intake has an extremely negative effect on kidney function. Protein (unlike fat) does not accumulate in the body, so all the "extra" protein and its breakdown products must be excreted by the kidneys. An excessive amount of protein in food significantly increases the load on the kidneys, and also leads to a change in the pH of urine ("acidifies" it), which in turn can lead to the formation of salts (oxalates, urates).

DISCUSSION

It is for this reason that fashionable protein diets are harmful to the kidneys. Protein diets are not balanced and often cause protein metabolism disorders. Each kidney is placed in a special fat capsule – to maintain optimal kidney working conditions. The fat layer protects the kidneys from shocks, cold, and supports them in their natural position. Diets that burn fat out of the body, in fact, deprive the kidneys of this protection. As a result, a double blow to the urinary system is obtained: it is necessary to filter the blood with a disturbed protein balance, while working in unfavorable conditions of reducing the fat capsule. A sharp weight loss during a diet can lead to such a serious condition as kidney prolapse. The abuse of too sweet or too salty food disrupts the water-salt balance in the body. At the same time, complete rejection of salt can also lead to impaired kidney function. Salt should be consumed in reasonable quantities. And this is a reasonable amount about three times less than our usual daily norm. Not eating enough food, you will quickly get used to its "new" taste and this will help balance the nutrition of a teenager.

Constipation contributes to poisoning the body with decay products. Signs of this poisoning may be increased fatigue, drowsiness, fatigue, pallor of the skin, possibly the appearance of acne. Instead of being excreted, harmful substances continue to be absorbed from the intestine into the blood and again and again enter the kidneys for purification. Filtration of decay products formed in the intestine during constipation has an extremely negative effect on the functioning of the kidneys.

Fatigue, overwork, disproportionate physical and psychological stress significantly weaken the body's resistance and general immunity. As a result, any infection that enters the body (for example, through the respiratory system) does not meet resistance and calmly reaches the kidneys. Such infectious attacks can greatly affect the urinary system of the body. Untreated diseases (untreated caries, decompensated form of chronic tonsillitis, etc.) are permanent foci of infection that can lead to the formation of kidney inflammation.

CONCLUSIONS

Reasonable physical activity (not hard physical labor!), sports clubs, dance studios, exercise in the morning, walking in the fresh air – will help to keep your body in great shape and facilitate the work of the kidneys. The most useful for the kidneys include parsley, dill, celery, rose hips, strawberries, cucumbers and pumpkin, but none of these products should be abused, the diet should be varied. If kidney diseases are detected, it is recommended to limit sour-milk cottage cheese, cheese, meat, chocolate, products with a high content of calcium and vitamin C. As we have already said – the norm of fluid for an adult is 2-2.5 liters per day (depending on the weight of the person). This norm also includes the liquid contained in food (soup, herbal infusions, green tea, compotes, high-quality drinking water). But it is better to limit coffee and strong black tea. Mineral water should be used with caution. Mineral water is, first of all, a medicine and therefore the approach to its consumption should be competent: the calculation of the volume of mineral water allowed for use per day is carried out taking into account the weight of the patient, the choice of the brand of mineral water and the duration of the course of admission is also important. Considering the above, it is necessary to start taking this or that mineral water after consulting a doctor, and not with the usual thirst. Prevention in adolescence helps to avoid the development of renal pathologies among the population.

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